

RAISING THE INTEREST OF YOUNG LEARNERS FOR LINGUISTIC SKILLS*P. Begbudieva¹, A. Roziboyev²**Abstract:*

This article emphasizes the importance of implementing new strategies to enhance the popularity of linguistic skills among the increasing number of young people, who are the future leaders. It highlights the crucial role of teachers' expertise and their instructional approaches tailored to students' learning abilities, ages, and other pertinent factors.

Key words: methods, modern technologies, internet, mindset, presidential decree, teachers' skills, linguistic skills, knowledge, languages, classes, professional education, English, brain work, grey matter, white matter., bilingual people

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Primarily, it's essential to note that there are approximately 6,500 languages worldwide, with English being the most prominent due to its dominance in international trade and politics. Lenneberg's theory underscores the significance of language acquisition between ages two and puberty, aligning with the brain's lateralization process. Recent neurological studies suggest varying time frames for lateralization, with most occurring before puberty [1]. Thus, it advocates for proactive teaching of linguistic skills during school years, serving as the cornerstone for future development, with adolescence offering a smoother path for skill refinement. Following the upheaval of the first two world wars, the global landscape shifted, with American businesses expanding trade worldwide, akin to Great Britain in the previous century, further cementing English as the lingua franca of global commerce.[4] This widespread use of English as a second language can be attributed to its global importance. To attain proficiency in English or integrate it as a second language resembling it to a mother tongue, we must raise a new generation with a strong linguistic foundation and a robust mindset, facilitated by the expertise of dedicated teachers. However, although English is the most popular language among people nowadays, it is recommendable that people do not have to stick to learning only English as the importance of other languages, from Portuguese to Chinese, is also abundant.

Then, to talk about the benefit of acquisition of linguistic skills, it is not only advantageous physically, when they are talking to some foreigner, but it is helpful for their brain work, as well. For instance, according to research held by Cambridge university, everyone's brain is made up of neurons, which have a cell body, and dendrites, which are the connections between neurons. This is what

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we call “grey matter.” Bilingual people have more of these neurons and dendrites compared to people who speak only one language. This means that their grey matter is denser. Bilingualism also has an impact on white matter – that is, a system of nerve fibres which connect all four lobes of the brain. This system coordinates communication between the different brain regions, helping your brain to learn and function. Bilingual adults have increased white matter integrity compared to adults who only speak one language. Their second language experience actually boosts their brain’s reserves [5].

Numerous campaigns were launched in Uzbekistan to enhance the development of foreign languages following the decree issued by the first President of Uzbekistan, Islom Karimov, on December 10, 2012, aimed at improving the education system for international languages. Furthermore, incumbent President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on the 6th may in 2020, made a video selector about developing the system for teaching international languages in Uzbekistan.

Sh. Mirziyoyev stated, “The time has come to establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must know at least two foreign languages perfectly. strict demand should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution” [3]. After such attention for language learning by the head of the country, every youngster should acquire a linguistic skill and develop it every day. After so many events, so many works that are being carried out nowadays, it will be shame if they do not learn other languages besides their own.

Nevertheless, teachers’ skills and their knowledge are also second to none in the improvement of child’s language-learning process. If a teacher has little or no experience in teaching and is perhaps now in a teacher education program, he/she may feel they cannot yet describe their own approach to learners. On the other hand, he/she might just surprise themselves at the intuitions they already have about pedagogical foundations [2]. Thus, it is better to be well-prepared for teachers before starting giving a lesson at educational places since under any circumstances, let it be excitement, nervousness, they can provide complete information about a practical topic. Currently, the government in Uzbekistan is establishing various classes for teachers to enhance their skills and professionalism in their respective fields. For example, language teaching teacher are being sent to universities in other regions around the country in every 5 years to strengthen their language. Furthermore, the decree of the head of state “On measures to support public education scientific-research services and introduction of professional development” [3] PD-4963 on the radical renewal of qualification control is introducing a new procedure in the field. That is, the current regulation, public education, that is, the involvement of teachers in training courses every 5 years. Now they will be able to improve their qualification level not once every 5 years, but every year, if possible - every day.

For this purpose, “continuing professional education” is introduced, considering the qualification of public education every year. According to the previous procedure, only 20 teachers were involved in the auxiliary qualification every year, but according to the new procedure, 100% of the teachers were involved in the qualification every year. Previously, 144 hours were taught in

qualification courses once every 5 years, but according to the new rules, teachers should be involved in at least 36 hours of studies every year [3].

In summary, in today's dynamic world, acquiring proficiency in language learning, offers significant advantages. Moreover, there is a constant need for educators who excel in their profession.

Furthermore, I firmly believe that if the upcoming generation possess a decent linguistic skill and build their life deploying this skill in different aspects of life, we can confidently entrust the future of our nation into their capable hands.

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